

An AI-enhanced multidisciplinary optimization framework for net-zero transport aircraft

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Outline

- HERWINGT project
- MDAO framework
- Generative AI for optimization
- Conclusions

HERWINGT

Project and scope

HERWINGT

The Hybrid Electric Regional Wing Integration Novel Green Technologies (HERWINGT) project is one of the game-changers to drive the transformation toward the decarbonization of aviation systems. It aims to **design a novel wing**, ideal for the future Hybrid-Electric Aircraft of the Regional Segment, and to **develop architectures, structures, and technologies** allowing higher integration of electric systems. Through these disruptive solutions, it will be pursued a **50% fuel burn reduction**, at the aircraft level compared to a 2020 state-of-the-art (SOTA) aircraft, in three different ways:

- Pioneering wing configurations and **improved aerodynamics** leading to drag reduction and enabling a fuel burn reduction of 15% at the wing component level, compared to a 2020 SOTA wing
- **Wing structures**, more integrated systems, and new material technologies resulted in a weight reduction of 20% at the component level, compared to a 2020 SOTA wing
- The development of technologies enabling the wing for a **hybrid-electrical** use case: H2/Batteries + fuel systems using Sustainable Aviation Fuels

MDAO framework

Development and industrialization

MDAO framework

Environment

- Gap between academic and industrial applications of MDAO is still large
 - High number of disciplines
 - Many in-house SW and internal know-how
 - Large set of requirements and constraints
- Academic cases focus on novelty, sometimes overlooking the complexity of real systems such as aircraft

M. Alder, E. Moerland, J. Jepsen and B. Nagel, "Recent Advances in Establishing a Common Language for Aircraft Design with CPACS," in *Aerospace Europe Conference*, Bordeaux, France, 2020.

Our approach

- Intuitive definition of systems and physical models (inspired on *Entity-Component-System* patterns and CPACS)
- Decoupled definition of disciplines and solver implementations to add flexibility
- Consistent definition of design and coupling variables
- Automatic coupling of disciplines and generation of dependency graphs

GEMSEO

<https://gemseo.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

MDAO framework

Mission

- Concatenation of segments
- Singly-linked list → missions can be branched

Components

- Containers of properties
- Can be nested
- *Parent* and *Connections* allow multiple hierarchies: geometry, fuel or electric systems...

MDAO framework

Variable

- Has a name, value and bounds

Discipline

- Physics simulation
- Initialized from components and solver options
- Defines its interface *dynamically*

MDAO framework. HERWINGT wing

MDAO framework. HERWINGT wing

MDAO framework. HERWINGT wing

Design variable	Lower bound	Upper bound
Root chord [m]	1.5	3.5
Kink position [-]	0.2	0.8
Zero-sweep line [-]	0.0	1.0
Tip/root chord ratio [-]	0.4	1.0
Tip twist [deg]	-5.0	5.0
Wing semi span [m]	10.0	30.0

MDAO framework. HERWINGT wing

<https://www.dust.polimi.it/>

Mission segment #1

- FL250 @ 400 KTAS
- 30 deg nose dive with load factor +2.5 g
- Maximum take off weight
- Sizing of the wing structure

Mission segment #2

- FL250 @ 320 KTAS
- Cruise flight covering 250 NM
- Maximum payload, using 80% of fuel (90%–10%)
- Design of the wing shape

MDAO framework

Generative AI for optimization

Probabilistic sampling

Generative AI for optimization

First population

- 100 individuals sampled with LHS
- All valid (tanks can carry all the fuel required)
- Optimum designs minimize variable mass: wing structure and fuel

Generative AI for optimization

Best individuals

Design / Objective	#1	#2	#3
Root chord	1.770	1.997	1.610
Kink position	0.507	0.725	0.790
Zero-sweep line	0.337	0.666	0.136
Tip/root chord ratio	0.719	0.924	0.640
Tip twist	-2.353	0.450	0.559
Wing semi span	22.370	18.993	28.340
Wing drag	2179.569	2073.174	1943.249
Wing mass	2328.450	2427.229	3345.206
Fuel mass	15189.450	16454.15	14632.26
Fuel fill ratio	0.466	0.443	0.415

Generative AI for optimization

- Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models are widely used and show state-of-the-art performance
- Starting from a completely *noisy* sample, they are trained to remove the noise incrementally, returning meaningful results

J. Ho, A. Jain and P. Abbeel, "Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vancouver, 2020.

$$q_\theta(\vec{x}_t|\vec{x}_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(\vec{x}_{t-1}; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t}\vec{x}_t, \beta_t\vec{I})$$

$$p_\theta(\vec{x}_{t-1}|\vec{x}_t) = \mathcal{N}(\vec{x}_t; \vec{\mu}_\theta(\vec{x}_t, \vec{y}_t, t), \Sigma_t\vec{I})$$

$$\Sigma_t = \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t$$

- In our case, the design variables play the role of the *image*, and the objectives and constraints condition the model

Generative AI for optimization

Model architecture

- The input vector contains the design variables, the time step and the conditioning
- The output vector only contains the mean of the Gaussian noise to be added to the design variables
- MLP with four layers
 - $11 \rightarrow 512 + \tanh$
 - $512 \rightarrow 1024 + \text{ReLu}$
 - $1024 \rightarrow 256 + \text{ReLu}$
 - $256 \rightarrow 6$
- 10% dropout during training

Generative AI for optimization

Generative AI for optimization

Proposed population

- 102 new individuals
- 80 valid (22 were out of bounds)
- Wing mass is well predicted
- Fuel mass is somewhat less consistent

Accuracy

Design space exploration

Population size and # of populations

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Holistic approaches are essential in the design of present and future aircraft
- MDAO methodologies can bring many benefits to industry, but they must be flexible enough to incorporate the existing know-how
- In our framework, we have successfully abstracted the definition of the system from the MDAO loops, automating the connection between the two
- The coupling with GEMSEO allows a wider range of applications, including uncertainty quantification or surrogate modelling
- The framework has been tested in the HERWINGT use case, including a representative subset of common disciplines in aircraft design
- Generative models based on AI could present an alternative to classical optimization algorithms
- Deep architectures can capture highly non-linear behaviors, providing samples that match well the requested performance

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